

A VERY SIMPLE PROOF OF FERMAT'S LAST THEOREM
Fermat's "marvelous proof"?

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Abstract

This article presents a very simple proof of Fermat's Last Theorem (FLT), which may be the "marvelous proof" he claimed to have, but which did not fit in the margin of the book he was reading (the Arithmetica of Diophantus of Alexandria). As a consequence of the proof, an alternative formulation of the Pythagorean terns is arrived at.

Statement of the theorem

If n is an integer greater than 2, there are no positive integers x, y, z , such that they satisfy the so-called "Fermat equation", in short, equation $[F]$.

$$x^n + y^n = z^n \quad [F]$$

About Fermat's equation

Fermat's equation is the most famous diophantine equation. A diophantine equation is an equation in which only constants and integer variables appear. In the case of $[F]$, there are no constants and the variables (x, y, z, n) represent positive integers.

We can assume that the triples (x, y, z) are primitive, i.e., that they have no common factor, i.e., $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$. If they did, then the initial equation could be reduced to one without that common factor.

Proof

In equation $[F]$, dividing x^n and y^n by z , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} x^n &= c_1 z + r_1 \\ y^n &= c_2 z + r_2 \end{aligned}$$

with c_i being the integer quotients and r_i being the remainders. Therefore, $0 \leq r_i < z$.

Adding both equations, and calling $c = c_1 + c_2$ and $r = r_1 + r_2$, we have:

$$z^n = cz + r \quad [G]$$

In this way, we have reduced the initial equation into a simpler, linear one, where the values c and r depend on x, y, z and n .

If either of the two remainders (r_1 or r_2) is zero, for example r_1 , we have:

$$\begin{aligned}x^n &= c_1z, & y^n &= c_2z + r_2 \\z^n &= c_1z + c_2z + r_2 \\z^n &= cz + r_2\end{aligned}$$

For the latter equation to be satisfied, r_2 must necessarily be a multiple of z , but $r_2 < z$. Therefore, it is impossible.

If $r = 0$, then:

$$\begin{aligned}r_1 &= r_2 = 0 \\x^n &= c_1z, & y^n &= c_2z \\z^n &= c_1z + c_2z = cz\end{aligned}$$

And x^n, y^n and z^n have a common factor, z , contrary to assumption. Therefore, r cannot be zero.

For equation $[G]$ to be satisfied, r must be a multiple of z . Since $0 < r < 2z$, it follows that $r = z$. The expressions x^n and y^n are linked because their remainders when divided by z are complementary to z . In this link lies the essence of the proof.

The equation $[G]$ becomes a simpler one:

$$z^n = cz + z \quad [Z]$$

On both sides of this equation there is a common factor (z). By eliminating it, $[Z]$ becomes the reduced equation $[R]$:

$$z^{n-1} = c + 1 \quad [R]$$

Equation $[R]$ reveals the true structure of equation $[F]$, its internal structure, the link $r_1 + r_2 = z$, which must exist for $[F]$ to be fulfilled.

Let's analyze the equation $[R]$, with $u_1 = c$, with a subscript because we are going to use a recursive procedure. The equation $[R]$ becomes $[R_1]$:

$$z^{n-1} = u_1 + 1 \quad [R_1]$$

This equation cannot be of the type $z^{n-1} = a^{n-1} + b^{n-1}$ because if it were, by applying to this expression the same procedure as above, we would arrive at the equation

$$z^{n-2} = u_2 + 1 \quad [R_2]$$

And so on until you get to the irreducible equation

$$z = u_{n-1} + 1 \quad [R_{n-1}]$$

Therefore, in equation $[R_1]$, the exponent of z must be equal to the exponent of z in $[R_{n-1}]$. In other words, the first reduction of $[F]$, which is $[R_1]$, must be the last possible reduction. It follows that $n - 1 = 1$ and $n = 2$.

With this result the theorem is proved: n cannot be greater than 2, i.e. the expression $r_1 + r_2 = z$ is only true when $n = 2$.

The new formula for Pythagorean triples

The Pythagorean triples fulfill the traditional equation $[T]$:

$$z^2 = x^2 + y^2 \quad [T]$$

The integer division between two positive integers, n_1 and n_2 , will be represented as $[n_1/n_2]$. Therefore, $c_1 = [x^n/z]$ and $c_2 = [y^n/z]$.

For $n = 2$, the equation $[R]$ is reduced to $z = c + 1$, i.e,

$$z = [x^2/z] + [y^2/z] + 1 \quad [P]$$

This equation is an alternative expression to the traditional one $[T]$ without the implicit common factor z . For example, for the triple $(3, 4, 5)$ it holds:

$$[3^2/5] + [4^2/5] + 1 = 1 + 3 + 1 = 5.$$

Andrew Wiles' proof

Since Pierre de Fermat posed his conjecture in 1637, all the great mathematicians have tried to prove it, without success. There have been proofs for certain particular cases of n , but not for the general case. Fermat himself proved it for $n = 4$.

Finally, the Englishman Andrew Wiles presented a proof in 1993, which failed in the first instance, but was corrected by Wiles himself with the help of a mathematician friend named Richard Taylor and finally published in 1995 [3, 5, 6]. The proof took 109 pages and required the use of advanced and sophisticated mathematical techniques, not at all intuitive and difficult to understand, even for professional mathematicians. Moreover, Wiles did not prove the theorem directly. He proved it as a corollary of another more general theorem, the Taniyama-Shimura theorem. The FLT is one of the great theorems in the history of mathematics.

Wiles' proof, in addition to solving an old mathematical problem, also developed new mathematical techniques and tools, which have paved the way for solving other mathematical problems, established new connections between different areas of mathematics, and have spurred the development of new areas of research.

Wiles spent many years working on the problem. With his feat, Wiles achieved worldwide fame, receiving numerous awards, including the Abel Prize, considered the Nobel Prize in Mathematics.

Contributions of the new proof

1. It demystifies the old FLT problem, considered "the most difficult mathematical problem in the world" [2]. And, paradoxically, it becomes one of the easiest. Sometimes the simplest is the most difficult to discover.
2. Gives credence to Fermat when he wrote in the margin of the copy of the book he was reading, "Arithmetica", by Diophantus of Alexandria [1, 4] that he had a "marvellous proof", but that he could not fit it in the margin. Given the complexity of Wiles' proof, most mathematicians believe that Fermat was mistaken in believing that he had such a marvellous proof.
3. Establishes a new formulation for the Pythagorean triples.
4. It highlights the power of simplicity in solving even the most seemingly difficult mathematical problems. A whole new paradigm that should be applied to the very foundations of mathematics. Complexity is just the combination of simple principles.
5. The FLT proof becomes accessible to a wider audience. It could even become popular and be used as a representative example of simplicity in mathematics.

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